

1 Ionogel-Based Electrodes for Non-Flammable High-Temperature Operating Electrochemical 2 Double-Layer Capacitors

3 Agnese Gamberini^{al}, Tobias Burton^{bl}, Alix Ladam^b, Ahmad Bagheri^a, Matteo Abruzzese^a, Hossein Beydaghi^a,
4 Valentina Mastronardi^a, Elena Calcagno^a, Samaneh Vaez^{a,c}, Alberto Morenghi^a, Teresa Gatti^c, Anais
5 Falgayrat^b, Francesco Bonaccorso^{a,*}, Sebastien Fantini^{b,*} and Sebastiano Bellani^{a,*}

6 ^a BeDimensional S.p.A., via Lungotorrente Secca 30R, Genova, 16163 Italy.

7 ^b Solvionic, 11 Chemin des Silos, Toulouse, 31100 France.

8 ^c Department of Applied Science and Technology, Politecnico di Torino, Corso Duca degli Abruzzi 24, 10129 Torino,
9 Italy.

10 ^l These authors equally contributed.

11 Corresponding Author: s.bellani@bedimensional.it; f.bonaccorso@bedimensional.it; sfantini@solvionic.com

12 *KEYWORDS. Electrochemical double-layer capacitors (EDLCs), ionic liquids (ILs), electrodes, ionogels,*
13 *temperature.*

14 Abstract

15 The design of interfaces between nanostructured electrodes and advanced electrolytes is critical for realizing
16 advanced electrochemical double-layer capacitors (EDLCs) that combine high charge-storage capacity, high-
17 rate capability, and enhanced safety. Toward this goal, this work presents a novel and sustainable approach for
18 fabricating ionogel-based electrodes using a renewed slurry casting method, in which the solvent is replaced
19 by the ionic liquid (IL), namely 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (EMIFSI). This
20 method avoids time-consuming and costly electrolyte-filling steps by integrating the IL directly into the
21 electrode during slurry preparation, while improving the rate capability of EDLCs based on pure non-
22 flammable ILs. The resulting ionogel electrodes demonstrate exceptional electrolyte accessibility and enable
23 the production of symmetric EDLCs with high energy density (over 30 Wh/kg based on electrode material
24 weight) and high-rate performance. These EDLCs could operate at temperatures up to 180°C, far exceeding
25 the limitations of traditional EDLCs based on organic electrolytes (e.g., 1 M TEABF₄ in acetonitrile, up to

26 65°C). Ionogel-type EDLCs exhibit remarkable long-term stability, retaining 88% specific capacity after 10000
27 galvanostatic charge/discharge cycles at 10 A g⁻¹ and demonstrating superior retention compared to
28 conventional EDLCs (50%), while also maintaining 92.4% energy density during 100 h floating tests at 2.7 V.
29 These electrochemical properties highlight their potential for robust performance under demanding conditions.
30 This study highpoints the practical potential of ionogel-based electrodes to advance IL-based EDLC
31 technology, paving the way for next-generation energy storage devices with high-temperature and high-voltage
32 operational capabilities.

33 1. Introduction

34 Electrochemical double-layer capacitors (EDLCs) are attractive electrochemical energy storage (EES) systems
35 that offer high-power density (>1000 W/kg, >500 W/L)^[1] and long cycle life (millions of charge/discharge
36 cycles) complementing battery specifications.^[1] Thus, they represent an ideal EES choice in automotive and
37 transportation sectors (*e.g.*, driving electronics for internal combustion engine vehicles and electric/hybrid
38 cars,^{[2],[3]} propulsion systems for electric buses and trams,^{[4],[5]} regenerative braking systems,^{[6],[7]} and
39 emergency power units in avionics and trains^[8]), smart grids (*e.g.*, backup generators,^{[9],[10]} peak shaving,^{[11],[12]}
40 and load balancing units^[13]), wind turbines (*e.g.*, pitch control systems^[5]) and power electronics (*e.g.*,
41 alternating current filters^[14]). Nevertheless, their energy density (typically <10 Wh/kg, <8 Wh/L at cell level
42 for commercial devices) must be increased to conveniently replace battery-type units, extending their
43 applications in other markets, including flexible and wearable electronics^[15] and aerospace sector.^{[16],[17]} Even
44 though EDLCs are not susceptible to thermal runaway phenomena that arise in other EES systems (*e.g.*, metal-
45 ion batteries^[18] and metal-ion hybrid capacitors^[19]),^[20,21] EDLC electrolytes are commonly based on flammable
46 and high-vapor pressure solvent (acetonitrile-based formulations, typically using tetraethylammonium
47 tetrafluoroborate (TEABF₄) as the electrolyte). Such organic electrolytes can cause internal pressure buildup
48 under temperature variations, restricting the operating temperature window of traditional EDLCs (*e.g.*, -
49 40/+65°C for commercial devices).^[22,23] In the automotive industry and other applications (*e.g.* wearable
50 electronic devices) wherein stringent safety requirements are imposed (sometimes under harsh environmental
51 conditions) replacing acetonitrile-based electrolytes is fast becoming a key focus.^[24] Towards that goal, ionic
52 liquid (IL) electrolytes have been the center of intense scientific and industrial attention.^[25] In fact, these salts,

53 which are liquid below 100°C, demonstrate unrivalled safety properties with flash points above 200°C and
54 negligible vapor pressure, making these compounds essentially non-flammable. However, their significantly
55 higher viscosities compared to conventional acetonitrile-based electrolytes limit the performance of IL-based
56 EDLCs. To overcome this challenge, various approaches have been explored to optimize ion
57 adsorption/desorption processes on electrodes, including ion-pore size matching and mixing ILs with organic
58 solvents.^[25] However, these strategies fail to fully address the existing limitations, emphasizing the need for
59 innovative approaches to overcome these challenges, while preserving the inherent safety and non-
60 flammability of ILs. To meet the increasingly stringent demands of future energy storage technologies, the
61 development of nanostructured electrode/electrolyte systems with enhanced charge-storage capabilities,
62 coupled with simplified and scalable manufacturing methods, remains a key focus in the advancement of
63 EDLCs.^[15]

64 In this work, we propose a novel approach for producing EDLCs with high energy densities (~30 Wh/kg,
65 referring to the electrode material weight) and with wide operating-temperature windows (up to 180°C). As
66 illustrated in **Scheme 1**, the novelty of this approach relies on the fabrication of electrodes in the form of IL-
67 based gels, namely ionogels, wherein networks of electrode materials networks enclose large amounts of ILs.
68 The latter are produced on the basis of the slurry casting method, which represents the most common current
69 industrial electrode manufacturing process.^[26] In our approach, however, the solvent of the slurry is replaced
70 by IL. Using ILs instead of solvents to produce electrodes and separators for energy storage devices has
71 recently been patented by Solvionic as an effective method for increasing the performance IL-based
72 devices.^{[27],[28]} Besides their well-known characteristics, including chemical, thermal, and electrochemical
73 stabilities, non-volatility and non-flammability, our ionogels intrinsically offer exceptional accessibility of the
74 electrolyte to the electrode surface being that the IL was intimately mixed with the electrode materials during
75 the electrode fabrication step. Consequently, the use of ionogels also simplifies conventional EDLC assembly
76 processes by omitting the need for the rigorous electrolyte filling/wetting step. The latter is a time-consuming
77 and cost-intensive process of EDLC manufacturing that determines the final device performances.^[29-33]
78 Conventionally, when assembling EDLCs, the electrolyte must be distributed uniformly into the cell,^[34] whilst
79 guarantying the removal of residuals gases.^[29] Therein, the aim is to maximize the total electrochemically
80 accessible surface area (SA) of the electrodes, thus maximizing the cell energy density.^[35] The electrolyte

81 filling step may even be repeated multiple times. However excess electrolyte in the cell must be avoided as
 82 that would decrease the gravimetric or volumetric performances of the EDLC. This step can require several
 83 days for high-SA electrodes,^[36] requiring vacuum (and optionally heating) to accelerate electrode soaking in a
 84 large-scale cell manufacturing chains.^[36-38] The electrolyte filling/wetting step may also depend on the cell
 85 configuration,^{[39],[40]} which, for the case of EDLCs, may be prismatic, cylindrical, or pouch formats.^[41] In
 86 ionogels, IL fills the pore volume of the electrodes, intrinsically eliminating gas entrapment and thus avoiding
 87 the need for specific electrolyte filling/wetting steps, which are not yet optimized for advanced electrode
 88 materials developed at R&D level. After proving the efficient wetting of the electrode materials with pure IL
 89 in our ionogels, symmetric EDLCs were assembled and characterized. These cells demonstrated high energy
 90 density combined with high-rate capability; outperforming devices produced with conventional electrodes that
 91 suffer from poor electrolyte-wettability. Finally, electrochemical characterization of our EDLCs was evaluated
 92 at different temperatures (up to 180°C) proving that safe power output is possible in conditions in which
 93 traditional EDLCs, as well as other EES devices (*e.g.*, metal-ion batteries), fail.^[42]

94

95 **Scheme 1.** Top: illustration of the production of ionogel-type electrodes. Bottom: representation of the
96 electrolyte wetting of conventional (solid-state) and ionogel-type electrodes.

97 **2. Methods**

98 **2.1. Materials.** Activated carbon (AC) powder (AB-520), styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR) and carboxymethyl
99 cellulose (CMC) binders, and conductive carbon-coated aluminium (C-coated Al) foils were purchased from
100 MTI Corp.

101 **2.2. Materials characterization.** Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) measurements were carried out using a
102 TGA Q500 (TA Instruments) thermogravimetric analyzer in N₂ flow from 40°C to 700°C at a heating rate of
103 10°C min⁻¹. Gas physisorption measurements were carried out using 3Flex Adsorption Analyzer
104 (Micromeritics). Specific SA analysis of the active materials was carried out by N₂ (purity 99.999%) adsorption
105 at liquid N₂ temperature (77.3 K). Before measurements, the powder sample was degassed at 250°C overnight
106 to remove any adsorbed species. The Brunauer, Emmett and Teller (BET) SA (S_{BET}) was calculated from the
107 N₂ adsorption isotherm using the multi-point BET method,^[43] considering equally spaced points in a relative
108 pressure range (P/P_0) from 0.01 to 0.30 with a correlation coefficient exceeding 0.999. Micropore analysis was
109 performed by CO₂ adsorption (purity 99.995%) at a temperature of 273.5 K. The measurements were
110 performed after N₂ physisorption measurements, degassing the sample at 200°C for 1 h. Pore size distribution
111 (PSD) of the sample was calculated by CO₂ adsorption isotherm using Density Functional Theory (DFT)
112 method^[38] in a P/P_0 range from 0.001 to 0.03.

113 **2.3. Electrodes fabrication.** Ionogels were produced by mixing AC, few-layer graphene (FLG), produced by
114 BeDimensional S.p.A. through wet-jet milling exfoliation of graphite,^[44-48] CMC:SBR (1:2.75 wt/wt) with a
115 90:5:5 weight ratio in a 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(fluorosulfonyl)imide (EMIFSI):water (1:1 wt/wt)
116 mixture (solid:liquid content ratio ~1:3 wt/wt) using a planetary centrifugal mixer, until obtaining a
117 homogenized slurry,^[49-51] in a method adapted from the process developed by Solvionic.^[27] The as-produced
118 slurry was subsequently deposited onto a C-coated Al foil by doctor blading using a MSK-AFA-H200A coater
119 (MTI Corp.). Conventional (solid-state) electrodes were also produced from aqueous slurry with the same
120 AC:FLG:CMC:SBR weight ratio. It is worth noting that ionogels can also be produced from water-free slurries
121 using ILs as the liquid media and binders such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) or polyvinylidene fluoride

122 (PVDF) that, however, are perfluoroalkyl and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS).^[27] To eliminate
123 environmentally and/or biologically hazardous chemicals (*e.g.*, F-containing carboxylic acids and/or
124 ammonium lauryl sulphate used as wetting agents to stabilize PTFE aqueous dispersions),^[52,53] herein non-
125 PFAS materials were explored, namely CMC:SBR binders and FSI-based ionic liquids (S-F bonds). The
126 electrodes were dried at 70°C in a vacuum oven (Binder, VD 53-UL) overnight. The electrodes were then cut
127 into 15 mm-diameter discs with MSK-T-07 compact precision disc cutter (MTI Corp.) followed by vacuum
128 drying (100°C for 3 h with a temperature ramp of 5°C min⁻¹), in a Büchi® B-585 glass oven connected to V-
129 300 vacuum pump to remove water residue. The electrodes were then transferred into an Ar-filled glove box
130 (MBRAUN UNIlab) in which EDLCs cells were then assembled. The mass loading of the electrode materials
131 was ~4 mg cm⁻² for better comparison with the specifications of commercially available EDLCs.^[54] Contact
132 angle measurements on the prepared IL-based electrodes demonstrated a contact angle of zero. This result
133 confirms the excellent wettability of the IL electrolyte on the ionogel-based electrodes.

134 **2.4. Assembly of EDLCs.** The EDLCs were fabricated by stacking two electrodes, separated by a cellulose
135 separator (Skeleton Technologies) in a Swagelok-type cell based on 316L stainless steel pistons, an insulating
136 PTFE-coated 316L stainless steel body, and PTFE sealing rings. EMIFSI (99.9%, Solvionic) was used as the
137 electrolyte. For high temperature (up to 180°C) tests, EDLCs were also produced in coin cell configuration
138 using 316L stainless steel CR2032 coin cell case, 316L stainless steel spring (Belleville washers), and 316L
139 stainless steel spacers (MTI Corp.). For these cells, grade GF/A glassy fibre separators (Whatman) were used
140 instead of cellulose one (which were used just for a reference coin cell tested at room temperature for
141 comparison purposes). Coin cell sealing was performed with an MSK-110 hydraulic crimper (MTI corp.) at a
142 pressure of 60 kg cm⁻². For comparison purposes, reference cells were also assembled with solid-state
143 electrodes using a standard organic electrolyte in commercial-like EDLCs, *i.e.*, 1 M tetraethylammonium-
144 tetrafluoroborate (TEABF₄) in acetonitrile. This electrolyte was formulated by mixing TEABF₄ (Sigma
145 Aldrich) with anhydrous acetonitrile (Sigma Aldrich) in the Ar-filled glove box.

146 **2.5. Electrochemical characterization.** Electrochemical measurements of the EDLCs were first performed at
147 room temperature using a potentiostat/galvanostat (VMP3, Biologic) station controlled *via* its own software.
148 Cyclic voltammetry (CV) measurements were performed at various voltage scan rates, from 5 mV s⁻¹ to 1000

149 mV s⁻¹, after 10 preconditioning cycles at 100 mV s⁻¹. Once the CVs were completed, galvanostatic
150 charge/discharge (GCD) curves were collected at specific currents ranging from 0.2 A g⁻¹ to 50 A g⁻¹. Hereafter,
151 specific current refers to the I/m_{el} ratio, in which I (A) is the applied current and m_{el} (g) is the mass of a single
152 electrode (excluding its current collector). The specific capacity (C_s) (A h g⁻¹) of the EDLC was used as an
153 universal metric to consider charge storage mechanisms that might deviate from ideal capacitive
154 behaviour,^{[49],[55],[56]} and was calculated from GCD profiles using $C_s = (I \times t_d) / (3600 \times m)$, in which I (A) is the
155 applied current, t_d (s) is the discharge time, and m (g) is the total mass of the electrodes (excluding current
156 collectors). In addition, the gravimetric capacity (C_g) (F g⁻¹) of the EDLCs was calculated from GCD profiles
157 using $C_g = (I \times t_d) / (V_r \times m)$ in which V_r is the rated voltage, *i.e.*, the max applied voltage (or operational voltage).
158 Noteworthy, $C_g = (C_s \times 3600) / V_r$. The discharge energy density (W h kg⁻¹), or discharge specific energy
159 (hereafter referred to just as energy density), of the EDLCs was calculated using the integral equation that
160 considers the non-linearity of galvanostatic discharge profiles.^{[49],[55],[56]} The charge energy density is calculated
161 similarly to the discharge energy density, except that the integral is calculated over the galvanostatic charge
162 profile. The average discharge power density (W kg⁻¹), or specific power (hereafter referred to just as power
163 density), of the EDLCs was calculated as average discharge power density = (discharge energy
164 density × 3600) / t_d. The Coulombic efficiency (CE) of the EDLCs was calculated using the ratio between t_d to
165 the charge time (t_c) of the GCD curve, *i.e.*, CE = t_d / t_c. The energy efficiency (EE) of the EDLCs is given by the
166 ratio between the discharge energy density and charge energy density. Maximum power density (P_{max}) of the
167 EDLCs was calculated as $P_{max} = V_r^2 / (4 \times ESR \times m)$, in which ESR is the equivalent series resistance. The latter
168 was estimated from the galvanostatic discharge profile as $ESR = \Delta V_{drop} / (2 \times I)$, in which V_{drop} is the voltage
169 drop measured at the initial stage of discharge step. The performances of EDLCs in coin cell configuration
170 were also evaluated as a function of the temperature, placing the devices on a temperature-resistant holder in
171 a mechanical convection oven. Metallic wires were used to bring the electrical contacts of the positive and
172 negative electrodes outside the oven. High-temperature extension cables (Biologic) were used for precaution.
173 The electrochemical stability of the EDLCs was preliminarily evaluated over 1000 GCD cycles. Afterwards,
174 floating tests (voltage hold protocols) were carried out on the EDLCs to assess their lifetime according to
175 industrial-like aging protocols, *e.g.*, standard IEC62391.^{[57],[58]} Floating tests were conducted by holding the
176 EDLCs at their V_r for 100 h and periodically conducting 5 GCD cycles at 1 A g⁻¹ to determine the cell

177 electrochemical performances. More in detail, GCD cycling was performed every 10 h, corresponding to a
178 single floating cycle. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements of the prepared EDLCs
179 were performed in the frequency range from 0.01 Hz to 500 kHz at the discharged state with an AC voltage
180 amplitude of 20 mV.

181 3. Results and discussion

182 The liquid electrolyte EMIFSI was selected for this study due to its high ionic conductivity, which ranks among
183 the best available ILs. This superior performance is partly attributed to its relatively low viscosity.^[59]
184 Furthermore, while the electrochemical stability window of imidazolium-based electrolytes is narrower than
185 that of pyrrolidinium counterparts, EMIFSI demonstrates stability comparable to state-of-the-art
186 electrolytes.^[60] Another reason for selecting this IL is its industrial maturity, as evidenced by Solvionic's pilot
187 production line with a capacity of 1.5 t/month. Ionogel-type electrodes were produced by depositing a slurry
188 of electrode materials using EMIFSI as the main liquid media. In the final electrodes, the weight content of
189 the electrode materials (excluding the current collectors) was 60 wt% for EMIFSI, 36 wt% for AC, 2 wt% for
190 FLG and 2 wt% for CMC:SBR. The miscibility of EMIFSI with water has allowed the use cheap water-soluble
191 binders, namely CMC:SBR. This avoids the use of common F-containing binders (*e.g.*, PTFE and PVDF)^[61]
192 that, in addition to being more expensive than aqueous binders, are dispersed in toxic solvents (*e.g.*, N-Methyl-
193 2-pyrrolidone -NMP- for PVDF) or are stably dispersed in water by environmentally and/or biologically
194 hazardous wetting agents (*e.g.*, fluorine-containing carboxylic acids and/or ammonium lauryl sulphate for
195 PTFE).^[52] Therefore, our IL-based ionogels intrinsically eliminate costs associated with the use, drying and
196 recovery of organic solvents (whose content in the slurry can amount to 50-70 wt%),^[27,37,62] an energy-intense
197 procedure compared to the low-temperatures required for (<120°C, in our case 70°C with vacuum) drying
198 water-processed electrodes.^[37,63,64] The presence of non-volatile ILs in the slurry ensures that the electrode
199 material surface remains optimally wet by the liquid electrolyte, avoiding gas trapping and the need for time-
200 consuming electrolyte filling/wetting steps in practical devices.^[27,29-33] **Fig. S1** shows the conductivity of
201 EMIFSI as a function of the temperature, from -10°C to 80°C. The data confirm that EMIFSI is a high-
202 conductivity IL, fulfilling essential specifications for high-power electrochemical energy storage devices.<sup>[65-
203 ^{67]} In general, FSI-based ILs display lower viscosities and higher conductivities than those containing</sup>

204 TFSI^[65,68,69] These properties can be associated with the small size of FSI⁻ anions ($\sim 95 \text{ \AA}^3$, smaller than the size
205 of TFSI⁻ anions, 147 \AA^3)^[70,71] as well as the flexibility of its structure ($-\text{SO}_2-\text{N}^{(-)}-\text{SO}_2-$),^[70,71] leading to
206 weak van der Waals interactions in the corresponding electrolyte systems.^[70,71] To prove the validity of our
207 approach, symmetric EDLCs were assembled with ionogel-type electrodes made of 90 wt% of AC (relative to
208 the solid content) and using pure EMIFSI as the non-flammable electrolyte. The electrochemical performances
209 of the ionogel-based EDLCs were measured with a V_r of 2.7 V and compared with those of reference devices
210 containing solid-state electrodes produced using the aqueous slurry casting method (see details in Methods).
211 **Fig. 1a** shows the comparison of the CV curves (plotted as C_g vs. voltage) measured for the investigated EDLCs
212 at two representative voltage scan rates, *i.e.*, 0.05 V s^{-1} and 1 V s^{-1} . The ionogel-type EDLCs shows higher C_g ,
213 especially at the highest voltage scan rate of 1 V s^{-1} in which the conventional EDLC exhibits a leaf-shaped
214 CV curve. The latter can be associated to resistive losses, including those resulting from the electrolyte
215 transport into porous electrodes. **Fig. 1b** reports the GCD profiles measured for the EDLCs at specific currents
216 of 10 A g^{-1} and 0.2 A g^{-1} , confirming the electrochemical behaviour observed from CV data. At the high specific
217 current of 10 A g^{-1} , the ionogel-type EDLC has a lower ΔV_{drop} than the conventional EDLC. In fact, the ESR
218 of the ionogel-type EDLC is reduced by 30% when compared to that of the conventional EDLC, thus enabling
219 high-power operations even in the presence of pure IL as the electrolyte. Consequently, the ionogel-type EDLC
220 exhibits a P_{max} of 479.6 kW kg^{-1} that is significantly superior to that of conventional EDLC (139.3 kW kg^{-1}).
221 The CV curves and GCD profiles measured for these EDLCs at various voltage scan rates and specific currents,
222 respectively, are reported in the Supporting Information (**Fig. S2-S5**). Noteworthy, the CV curves of the
223 EDLCs feature specific currents that increase with increasing voltage, leading to butterfly-like shapes. The
224 latter are commonly observed for devices based on active carbonaceous materials,^[72,73] and have been
225 associated with the dependence of the quantum capacitance of graphitic materials as a function of the voltage
226 associated with a potential-dependent density of state (*i.e.*, their charge carrier density increases with the
227 position of the Fermi level within the density of state).^[72,73] Consistently with CV data, the GCD profiles show
228 quasi-triangular shapes, with voltage-dependent slopes of the GCD profiles, indicating voltage-dependent
229 capacitance. **Fig. 1c** shows the rate capability of the EDLCs wherein C_s and the CE are plotted as a function
230 of the specific current. Importantly, C_s was plotted as a universal metric instead of C_g to consider the non-
231 linearity of the GCD profiles.^[74] Despite the deviation from an ideal capacitive behaviour, the EDLCs exhibit

232 CEs approaching 100%, excluding Faradaic effects. **Fig. 1d** shows the Ragone plots (energy density vs. power
233 density) measured for the investigated EDLCs, as calculated using the GCD data, illustrating the superior rate
234 capability of the ionogel-type EDLCs compared to that of conventional EDLCs. At the power density of 12.96
235 kW kg⁻¹, the ionogel-type EDLC retains ~83% of the energy density measured at the lowest power density of
236 0.14 kW kg⁻¹. Contrarily, the energy density of conventional EDLCs drops by 65.4% when increasing the
237 power density from 0.14 kW kg⁻¹ (29.2 Wh kg⁻¹) to 8.67 kW kg⁻¹ (10.1 Wh kg⁻¹). The Ragone plot obtained for
238 ionogel-type EDLCs operating at a V_r of 3.0 V is also shown, confirming the high-rate capability of this device
239 configuration together with remarkable energy densities higher than 30 Wh kg⁻¹ (*e.g.*, 36.6 Wh kg⁻¹ at 0.77 kW
240 kg⁻¹). By normalizing the energy of the EDCLs by the weight of the active material only, a metric often reported
241 in literature,^[75] energy densities as high as 40.7 Wh kg⁻¹ are obtained for ionogel-type EDLCs. The CV and
242 GCD data recorded for ionogel-type EDLCs operating at V_r of 3.0 V are reported in the Supporting Information
243 (**Fig. S6-S7**). For comparison purposes, the electrochemical characterization of a conventional EDLC using a
244 standard organic electrolyte (1 M TEABF₄ in acetonitrile) is also reported in Supporting Information (**Fig. S8**).
245 Importantly, despite the use of a more viscous electrolyte, the proposed ionogel-type EDLC shows
246 performances (C_s, energy density, CE/EE, and rate capability) comparable to those of conventional EDLCs
247 based on commercial-like organic electrolyte, which is however flammable and not able to operate at high
248 temperatures (*e.g.*, ≥70°C).

249

250 **Fig. 1.** a) CV curves measured for ionogel-type and conventional EDLCs at voltage scan rates of 0.05 V s⁻¹
 251 and 1 V s⁻¹. b) GCD profiles measured for ionogel-type and conventional EDLCs at the specific current of 10
 252 A g⁻¹. The inset panel shows the GCD profiles of the investigated EDLCs measured at a specific current of 0.2
 253 A g⁻¹. c) C_s (left y-axis) and CE (right y-axis) vs. specific current plots measured for ionogel-type and
 254 conventional EDLCs at V_r = 2.7 V. d) Ragone plots measured for ionogel-type and conventional EDLCs at V_r
 255 = 2.7 V. The Ragone plot measured for ionogel-type EDLC at V_r = 3.0 V is also shown for comparison.
 256 Electrolyte: EMIFSI.

257 Considering the non-solid-state form of our ionogel-type electrodes, it is crucial to evaluate possible drawbacks
 258 related to the stability of the electrode/current collector interfaces. The electrochemical stability of the devices
 259 was preliminarily evaluated over GCD cycling, checking a relatively limited number of cycles, *i.e.*, 1000,
 260 before moving towards more demanding industrial-like protocols, *i.e.*, floating tests.^[57] **Fig. 2** shows the GCD
 261 cycling of the ionogel-type EDLCs operating at V_r of 2.7 V over 1000 cycles at 10 A g⁻¹, showing satisfactory
 262 energy density retention (93.8%) even superior to that of conventional EDLC (84.9%) (**Fig. S9a**). The cyclic

263 instability of the latter may be associated to the high viscosity of the electrolyte, *i.e.*, pure EMIFSI (24.5 cP at
264 25°C^[76] vs. ~0.2 cP for 1 M TEABF₄ in ACN^[77]), which may encounter difficulties in accessing the SA of
265 porous active materials of EDLCs operating at high specific currents, causing electromechanical stresses. The
266 investigated EDCLs also demonstrated a satisfactory performance stability during the floating test at V_r of 2.7
267 V, retaining 100% of the initial C_s and 92.4% of the initial energy density (measured at 1 A g⁻¹). Similar
268 behaviour was recorded for the conventional EDLC (Fig. S8b).

269

270

271 **Fig. 2.** a) Cyclic stability of the ionogel-type EDLC: C_s (left y-axis) and energy density (right y-axis) vs. cycle
272 number plots measured at 10 A g⁻¹ and V_r = 2.7 V. b) Floating stability of the ionogel-type EDLC: C_s (left y-
273 axis) and energy density (right y-axis) vs. float time plots measured at 1 A g⁻¹ and V_r = 2.7 V. Electrolyte:
274 EMIFSI.

275 To exploit the combination of high-rate capability combined with the use of EMIFSI as a non-flammable
276 electrolyte, the characterization of our ionogel-type EDLCs was extended to high temperatures ranging from

277 25 to 180°C. In case of temperature-related damage, coin cell systems were chosen for these tests as they are
278 much more affordable compared to Swagelok systems. Also, glassy fiber separators were used instead of
279 cellulose ones to ensure that all the cell components were thermally and dimensionally stable up to
280 temperatures as high as 200 °C, even though the large thickness of the former (0.26 mm) results in EDLCs
281 with high ESRs (*ca.* an order of magnitude higher than those obtained with cellulose separators).
282 Thermogravimetric analysis measurements of the cell components are reported in **Fig. S10**.

283 Preliminary tests in EDCLs with coin cell configurations using cellulose separators revealed very similar
284 performances (energy density and rate capability) compared to Swagelok-type devices (**Fig. S11**) whilst also
285 confirming that the ionogel-type EDLCs significantly outperform conventional EDLCs when using EMIFSI
286 as the electrolyte. Nevertheless, the cyclic stability of EDLCs in coin cell configurations operating at V_r of 2.7
287 V was inferior to that of devices in Swagelok cell configuration (**Fig. S12 vs. Fig. 2a**), likely due to the lower
288 pressure applied to the electrode/separator/electrode stack, leading to a progressive increase of the ESR, as
289 also observed over prolonged cycling at a conservative V_r of 2.4 V (**Fig. S13**). Discrepancies between the
290 lifetimes of different prototypes come down to cell design, as discussed in relevant literature.^[57] When using
291 FSI-based electrolytes, FSI⁻ anions can attack the passivating oxide layer of the positive aluminium current
292 collectors generating insoluble Al-FSI compounds $-Al(FSI)_3$.^[78-80] This effect is well-known in Li-ion
293 batteries, affecting the cathode current collector at potentials higher than 4.0 V vs. Li/Li⁺.^[78,79,81,82] This effect
294 is however less studied in EDLCs even though the upper potentials reached by the positive electrodes are
295 comparable to those at which Li-ion battery cathodes operate.^[80] In this context, the increase of stack pressure
296 can effectively reduce performance fade by keeping an intimate contact between the electrode material and
297 current collector, thus suppressing electrode delamination.^[83,84] Since the FSI-induced aluminium corrosion
298 and other parasitic reactions such as electrolyte solvent/salt decomposition and electrode material
299 modifications,^[80] are exacerbated when increasing the temperature,^[79] our electrochemical tests were
300 conducted by progressively decreasing V_r as the temperature increased, with the aim of ensuring sufficient
301 cyclic stability. The electrochemical characterizations of ionogel-type EDLCs operating at 100°C and 140°C
302 were measured with maximum V_r values of 2.4V and 1.8V, respectively (see **Fig. S14-S15**), at which no
303 degradation was observed during these GCD analysis. At 180°C and with a V_r value of 1.6 V (**Fig. S16**), the
304 devices underwent degradation during GCD analysis when the specific current was decreased from 20 A g⁻¹ to

305 1 A g⁻¹. Based on this preliminary performance assessment, GCD analysis was then performed with a specific
 306 current of 1 A g⁻¹, increasing progressively V_r until device exhibited insufficient CE (<90%), *i.e.*, showing
 307 significant parasitic reactions. **Fig. 3** reports the energy density of the EDLCs measured for different V_r and
 308 temperature combinations. Ionogel-type EDLCs exhibit a nearly temperature-independent energy density for
 309 fixed V_r. Even though the conductivity of the ionic liquid increases with increasing temperature, ionogel-type
 310 electrodes intrinsically offer optimal electrolyte accessibility without showing a temperature-dependent
 311 behaviour of the energy density measured at 1 A g⁻¹. Importantly, devices exhibited similar ESRs at
 312 temperatures below 180°C (**Fig. 3b**), which again supports an interesting temperature-independent behavior.
 313 However, the ESR recorded at 180°C increased significantly (*ca.* three times more) compared to those
 314 measured at lower temperatures. The increase of the ESR at such elevated temperatures can reasonably be
 315 attributed to the deterioration of the current collector/electrode material interface at the positive electrode, as
 316 caused by FSI-induced corrosion, which is exacerbated with the increase of the temperature.^[79] Prospectively,
 317 strategies that avoid parasitic reactions could be implemented, thus eliminating the need of a reduced V_r at
 318 high temperatures and yielding very stable ionogel-type EDLCs. Examples of strategies include the
 319 optimization of the electrode mass ratio to limit the maximum potential of the positive electrode^[85] and the use
 320 of Al-passivating additives,^[80,86] as well as the use of other ILs less corrosive than EMIFSI.

321
 322 **Fig. 3.** a) Energy densities and b) ESRs of ionogel-type EDLCs at various temperatures, extrapolated from
 323 GCD profiles measured with a specific current of 1 A g⁻¹ and increasing progressively V_r until devices operated
 324 with CE >90%. Electrolyte: EMIFSI.

325 To further evaluate the electrochemical performance and thermal stability of ionogel-type EDLCs operating
326 with V_r of 2.7 V, GCD cycles and EIS were performed at room temperature and 60°C. At room temperature,
327 the electrodes demonstrated excellent cyclic stability, maintaining almost 90% of their initial C_s over 10000
328 cycles at 10 A g⁻¹ (**Fig. 4a**). This stability is attributed to the preservation of the electrode structure, stable ion-
329 accessible SA, and minimal thermal stress on the electrolyte, ensuring a stable electrode/electrolyte interface
330 and efficient ion transport. Conversely, at 60°C, the electrodes displayed reduced stability, likely due to the
331 corrosive nature of FSI, highlighting the need for long-term anticorrosion strategies to enable practical
332 applications. The EIS analysis provided valuable insights into the electrochemical behaviour before and after
333 GCD cycling. At room temperature (**Fig. 4b**), the Nyquist plot exhibited near-ideal EDLC characteristics, with
334 a small semicircle in the high-frequency region indicating low charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}). In the low-
335 frequency region, the ionogel-type device demonstrated near-vertical behaviour, signifying excellent
336 capacitive performance. Prolonged cycling resulted in a slight increase in the semicircle diameter, indicating
337 a marginal rise in R_{ct} , consistent with the performance retention observed in **Fig. 4a**. After cycling, minor
338 deviations from the vertical line and increased Warburg impedance suggest modest changes in ion diffusion
339 processes within the ionogel-based electrodes. At 60°C (**Fig. 4c**), the as-fabricated EDLCs have shown Nyquist
340 plot with a smaller semicircle in the high-frequency region compared to the room-temperature case, indicating
341 minimal R_{ct} and efficient ion transport. However, after 6000 cycles, the semicircle became more pronounced,
342 reflecting a performance degradation accelerated by temperature. The low-frequency region initially displayed
343 ideal capacitive behavior, but deviations post-cycling indicated an increase of the ion diffusion resistance,
344 which we ascribed to FSI-induced corrosion effects, a challenge that we are now working on to address market
345 requirements.

346 **Fig. S16a** illustrates the stability of an EDLC based on EMIFSI electrolyte but with conventional electrodes.
347 This device retained only ~50% of its C_s after 10000 cycles, indicating a lower cyclic stability compared the
348 ionogel-type EDLCs. **Fig. S16b** shows the Nyquist plot of this devices, highlighting larger R_{ct} compared to
349 that resulting from ionogel-type electrodes. The large R_{ct} associated with conventional electrodes is linked to
350 high viscosity of EMIFSI, leading to a poor electrolyte wetting of the electrode SA. In the low-frequency
351 region, a Warburg tail reflects hindered ion diffusion. Overall, this analysis further remarks the benefits of
352 using ionogel-type electrodes in EDLCs based on advanced IL-based electrolyte with superior safety (*e.g.*,

353 non-flammability). **Table S1** compares the performance metrics of the prepared ionogel-type EDLCs with
 354 those reported in relevant literature.

355

356 **Fig. 4.** Electrochemical stability of ionogel-type EDLCs in coin cell configuration operating at room
 357 temperature and 60°C with a V_r of 2.7 V. a) Cyclic stability of ionogel-type EDLCs: C_s (left y-axis) and energy
 358 density (right y-axis) vs. cycle number plots measured at 10 A g^{-1} . Nyquist plots of the investigated ionogel-
 359 type EDLCs before and after GCD cycles at b) room temperature and c) 60°C .

360

361 4. Conclusions

362 In summary, we propose a novel approach to manufacture EDLC electrodes relying on the use of ILs as the
 363 liquid media for the slurry preparation. These electrodes can be produced using the conventional casting
 364 method used for the massive preparation of EDLC electrodes at industrial levels without any change. The
 365 resulting electrodes present in the form of ionogels wherein the electrolyte has exceptional accessibility to the

366 electrode surface due to the intimate mixing of the IL with the electrode materials in the slurry state.
367 Prospectively, our ionogel-type electrodes simplify the fabrication of EDLCs by avoiding the rigorous
368 electrolyte filling/wetting steps, which are time-consuming and cost-intensive.^[29–33] After producing ionogel-
369 type electrodes with a representative IL (EMIFSI), symmetric EDLCs were assembled using EMIFSI as a non-
370 flammable and thermally stable electrolyte. Room temperature electrochemical characterization demonstrated
371 that our ionogel-type EDLCs exhibited high energy density (over 30 Wh kg⁻¹) combined with high-rate
372 capability, outperforming devices produced with conventional electrodes. Lastly, electrochemical
373 characterization of our ionogel-type EDLCs was performed at temperatures up to 180°C, demonstrating the
374 feasibility of very high-temperature operations. This technology opens the door to new types of high energy
375 density applications operating in harsh conditions in which traditional EDLCs based on organic electrolytes
376 (*e.g.*, 1 M TEABF₄ in acetonitrile) fail. Prospectively, our approach can be extended to other types of IL-based
377 electrolytes. Additionally, further development of the individual components (including the electrolyte, current
378 collectors, active materials, and binder) for high-temperature conditions may further enhance the performance
379 of our ionogel-type EDLCs.

380 **ASSOCIATED CONTENT**

381 Supporting Information, including: CV and GCD measurements for ionogel-type EDCLs operating with
382 different V_r (2.7 V and 3.0 V); electrochemical characterization of conventional EDLCs using a standard
383 organic electrolyte (1 M TEABF₄ in acetonitrile) and operating with a V_r of 2.7 V; cyclic and floating stability
384 of conventional EDLCs using EMIFSI as the electrolyte; TGA profiles measured for EDCL components;
385 electrochemical characterization of EDLCs in coin cell format. ESR of ionogel-type EDCLs (coin cell) over
386 GCD cycling; electrochemical characterization of ionogel-type EDCLs operating at high temperature (from
387 100°C to 180°C).

388 **AUTHOR INFORMATION**

389 **Author Contributions**

390 A. G. and A. B. led the experimental activities, producing and characterizing the electrodes and EDLCs. A. B.
391 M. A, H. B., V. M., S. V., S.B. supported electrochemical characterization and electrochemical data analysis.

392 E. C carried out TGA measurements. T. B, A. L., A. F. and S. F. conceived the ionogel-pe electrodes. S. B., S.
393 F. and F. B supervised the activities and acquired the financial support. A. G. and S. B. wrote the original draft.
394 The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final
395 version of the manuscript. † These authors contributed equally.

396 **ACKNOWLEDGMENT**

397 **Funding Sources**

398 This project received funding from the European Union’s GREENCAP Horizon Europe research and
399 innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 101091572 and 2D-PRINTABLE Horizon Europe research
400 and innovation program under Grant Agreement No. 694101. S.V. acknowledges financial support from
401 the European Union Next Generation EU program (D.M. 117 del 02/03/2023 Ministero dell'Università e della
402 Ricerca)

403 **ETHICS**

404 **Notes**

405 A. G., A. B., M. A., H. B., V. M., E. C., A. M., and F. B. are employees of BeDimensional S.p.A., a company
406 that is commercializing 2D materials.

407 T. B., A. A., A. F and S. F are employees of Solvionic, a company that produces electrolytic grade ionic
408 liquid for batteries and supercapacitors.

409 **Reference**

- 410 [1] P. Simon, Y. Gogotsi, *Nature Materials* **2008**, *7*, 845–854.
- 411 [2] L. Guo, P. Hu, H. Wei, *Journal of Energy Storage* **2023**, *65*, 107269.
- 412 [3] D. Lemian, F. Bode, *Energies* **2022**, *15*, 5683.
- 413 [4] H. Y. Tong, *Sustainable Cities and Society* **2019**, *48*, 101588.
- 414 [5] G. Navarro, J. Torres, M. Blanco, J. Nájera, M. Santos-Herran, M. Lafoz, *Energies* **2021**, *14*, 3060.
- 415 [6] F. Naseri, E. Farjah, T. Ghanbari, *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology* **2017**, *66*, 3724–3738.

- 416 [7] S. Manoharan, K. Krishnamoorthy, A. Sathyaseelan, S.-J. Kim, *Materials Chemistry Frontiers* **2021**,
417 5, 6200–6211.
- 418 [8] B. Wang, C. Wang, Z. Wang, S. Ni, Y. Yang, P. Tian, *Energy* **2023**, 263, 125632.
- 419 [9] G. Stana, K. Kroics, in *2022 IEEE 20th International Power Electronics and Motion Control*
420 *Conference (PEMC)*, **2022**, pp. 467–473.
- 421 [10] A. Lahyani, P. Venet, A. Guermazi, A. Troudi, *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics* **2013**, 28,
422 1509–1522.
- 423 [11] P. Zhao, J. Wang, Y. Dai, *Renewable Energy* **2015**, 75, 541–549.
- 424 [12] F. Kamarulazam, S. Bashir, R. Subramaniam, R. Kasi, S. S. Ashok Sharma, *Energy Technology* **2022**,
425 10, 2101055.
- 426 [13] M. C. Argyrou, C. C. Marouchos, S. A. Kalogirou, P. Christodoulides, *Energy Reports* **2021**, 7,
427 4988–5002.
- 428 [14] S. Zhang, B. Li, C. Cui, W. Qian, Y. Jin, *Batteries & Supercaps* **2023**, 6, e202200566.
- 429 [15] P. Simon, Y. Gogotsi, *Nature Materials* **2020**, 19, 1151–1163.
- 430 [16] J. Gonzalez-Llorente, A. A. Lidtke, K. Hatanaka, L. Limam, I. Fajardo, K.-I. Okuyama, *Acta*
431 *Astronautica* **2020**, 174, 294–305.
- 432 [17] T. Shimizu, C. Underwood, *Acta Astronautica* **2013**, 85, 138–154.
- 433 [18] B. Liu, Y. Jia, C. Yuan, L. Wang, X. Gao, S. Yin, J. Xu, *Energy Storage Materials* **2020**, 24, 85–112.
- 434 [19] W. Zhou, Z. Liu, W. Chen, X. Sun, M. Luo, X. Zhang, C. Li, Y. An, S. Song, K. Wang, X. Zhang,
435 *Batteries* **2023**, 9, 128.
- 436 [20] A. Bagheri, S. Bellani, H. Beydaghi, Z. Wang, A. Morag, M. I. Zappia, J.-K. Panda, S. Vaez, V.
437 Mastronardi, A. Gamberini, S. B. Thorat, M. Abruzzese, R. Dong, L. Pasquale, M. Yu, X. Feng, F.
438 Bonaccorso, *ChemSusChem* **2024**, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cssc.202401454>.
- 439 [21] J. Wu, *Chemical Reviews* **2022**, 122, 10821–10859.

- 440 [22] A. Bagheri, S. Taghavi, S. Bellani, P. Salimi, H. Beydaghi, J. K. Panda, M. Isabella Zappia, V.
441 Mastronardi, A. Gamberini, S. Balkrishna Thorat, M. Abruzzese, L. Pasquale, M. Prato, M.
442 Signoretto, X. Feng, F. Bonaccorso, *Chemical Engineering Journal* **2024**, 496, 153529.
- 443 [23] M. A. Garakani, S. Bellani, V. Pellegrini, R. Oropesa-Nuñez, A. E. D. R. Castillo, S. Abouali, L.
444 Najafi, B. Martín-García, A. Ansaldo, P. Bondavalli, C. Demirci, V. Romano, E. Mantero, L.
445 Marasco, M. Prato, G. Bracciale, F. Bonaccorso, *Energy Storage Materials* **2021**, 34, 1–11.
- 446 [24] H. Van T. Nguyen, K.-K. Lee, *ChemSusChem* **2023**, 16, e202300756.
- 447 [25] K. C. Lethesh, M. O. Bamgbopa, R. A. Susantyoko, *Frontiers in Energy Research* **2021**, 9, 1–16.
- 448 [26] M. Faraji Niri, C. Reynolds, L. A. A. Román Ramírez, E. Kendrick, J. Marco, *Energy Storage*
449 *Materials* **2022**, 51, 223–238.
- 450 [27] R. Lin, A. Falgayrat, C. Aravena, S. Fantini, *Method and Apparatus for Making Electrodes for an*
451 *Ionic Liquid Based Supercapacitor, and Method for Making Such a Supercapacitor*, 2022, Patent WO
452 2020260444A1.
- 453 [28] *Method for Preparing an Electrode with High Load per Unit of Mass Filled with Electrolyte for a*
454 *Battery with High Energy Density*, 2022, Patent WO2022136810A1.
- 455 [29] M. P. Lautenschlaeger, B. Prifling, B. Kellers, J. Weinmiller, T. Danner, V. Schmidt, A. Latz,
456 *Batteries & Supercaps* **2022**, 5, e202200090.
- 457 [30] N. Kaden, R. Schlimbach, Á. Rohde García, K. Dröder, *Batteries* **2023**, 9, 164.
- 458 [31] A. Shodiev, E. Primo, O. Arcelus, M. Chouchane, M. Osenberg, A. Hilger, I. Manke, J. Li, A. A.
459 Franco, *Energy Storage Materials* **2021**, 38, 80–92.
- 460 [32] C. Sauter, R. Zahn, V. Wood, *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **2020**, 167, 100546.
- 461 [33] A. Schilling, P. Gümbel, M. Möller, F. Kalkan, F. Dietrich, K. Dröder, *Journal of The*
462 *Electrochemical Society* **2019**, 166, A5163.
- 463 [34] S. Jayaraman, T. J. Rawson, M. A. Belyustina, *Energy & Environmental Science* **2022**, 15, 2948–

- 464 2957.
- 465 [35] D. H. Jeon, *Energy Storage Materials* **2019**, *18*, 139–147.
- 466 [36] T. Knoche, V. Zinth, M. Schulz, J. Schnell, R. Gilles, G. Reinhart, *Journal of Power Sources* **2016**,
467 *331*, 267–276.
- 468 [37] D. L. Wood, J. Li, C. Daniel, *Journal of Power Sources* **2015**, *275*, 234–242.
- 469 [38] A. Davoodabadi, J. Li, H. Zhou, D. L. Wood, T. J. Singler, C. Jin, *Journal of Energy Storage* **2019**,
470 *26*, 101034.
- 471 [39] W. J. Weydanz, H. Reisenweber, A. Gottschalk, M. Schulz, T. Knoche, G. Reinhart, M. Masuch, J.
472 Franke, R. Gilles, *Journal of Power Sources* **2018**, *380*, 126–134.
- 473 [40] F. J. Günter, S. Rössler, M. Schulz, W. Braunwarth, R. Gilles, G. Reinhart, *Energy Technology* **2020**,
474 *8*, 1801108.
- 475 [41] D. Bhattacharjya, D. Carriazo, J. Ajuria, A. Villaverde, *Journal of Power Sources* **2019**, *439*, 227106.
- 476 [42] X. Lin, M. Salari, L. M. R. Arava, P. M. Ajayan, M. W. Grinstaff, *Chemical Society Reviews* **2016**,
477 *45*, 5848–5887.
- 478 [43] S. Brunauer, P. H. Emmett, E. Teller, *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **1938**, *60*, 309–319.
- 479 [44] A. E. Del Rio Castillo, V. Pellegrini, A. Ansaldo, F. Ricciardella, H. Sun, L. Marasco, J. Buha, Z.
480 Dang, L. Gagliani, E. Lago, N. Curreli, S. Gentiluomo, F. Palazon, M. Prato, R. Oropesa-Nuñez, P. S.
481 Toth, E. Mantero, M. Crugliano, A. Gamucci, A. Tomadin, M. Polini, F. Bonaccorso, *Materials*
482 *Horizons* **2018**, *5*, 890–904.
- 483 [45] S. Bellani, E. Petroni, A. E. Del Rio Castillo, N. Curreli, B. Martín-García, R. Oropesa-Nuñez, M.
484 Prato, F. Bonaccorso, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2019**, *29*, 1807659.
- 485 [46] H. Beydaghi, S. Abouali, S. B. Thorat, A. E. Del Rio Castillo, S. Bellani, S. Lauciello, S.
486 Gentiluomo, V. Pellegrini, F. Bonaccorso, *RSC Advances* **2021**, *11*, 35051–35060.
- 487 [47] S. Levchenko, V. Marangon, S. Bellani, L. Pasquale, F. Bonaccorso, V. Pellegrini, J. Hassoun, *ACS*

- 488 *Applied Materials & Interfaces* **2023**, *15*, 39218–39233.
- 489 [48] M. I. Zappia, V. Mastronardi, S. Bellani, Y. Zuo, G. Bianca, L. Gabatel, M. Gentile, A. Bagheri, H.
490 Beydaghi, F. Drago, M. Ferri, M. Moglianetti, P. P. Pompa, L. Manna, F. Bonaccorso,
491 *Electrochimica Acta* **2023**, *462*, 142696.
- 492 [49] M. Eredia, S. Bellani, M. I. Zappia, L. Gabatel, V. Galli, A. Bagheri, H. Beydaghi, G. Bianca, I.
493 Conticello, V. Pellegrini, F. Bonaccorso, *APL Materials* **2022**, *10*, 101102.
- 494 [50] A. Bagheri, S. Bellani, H. Beydaghi, M. Eredia, L. Najafi, G. Bianca, M. I. Zappia, M. Safarpour, M.
495 Najafi, E. Mantero, Z. Sofer, G. Hou, V. Pellegrini, X. Feng, F. Bonaccorso, *ACS Nano* **2022**, *16*,
496 16426–16442.
- 497 [51] M. Najafi, S. Bellani, V. Galli, M. I. Zappia, A. Bagheri, M. Safarpour, H. Beydaghi, M. Eredia, L.
498 Pasquale, R. Carzino, S. Lauciello, J.-K. Panda, R. Brescia, L. Gabatel, V. Pellegrini, F. Bonaccorso,
499 *Electrochem* **2022**, *3*, 463–478.
- 500 [52] D. Bresser, D. Buchholz, A. Moretti, A. Varzi, S. Passerini, *Energy & Environmental Science* **2018**,
501 *11*, 3096–3127.
- 502 [53] Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) - ECHA, [https://echa.europa.eu/hot-](https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/perfluoroalkyl-chemicals-pfas)
503 [topics/perfluoroalkyl-chemicals-pfas](https://echa.europa.eu/hot-topics/perfluoroalkyl-chemicals-pfas), accessed on 22/12/2024.
- 504 [54] Y. Gogotsi, P. Simon, *Science* **2011**, *334*, 917–918.
- 505 [55] A. Laheäär, P. Przygocki, Q. Abbas, F. Béguin, *Electrochemistry Communications* **2015**, *60*, 21–25.
- 506 [56] A. Noori, M. F. El-Kady, M. S. Rahmanifar, R. B. Kaner, M. F. Mousavi, *Chemical Society Reviews*
507 **2019**, *48*, 1272–1341.
- 508 [57] P. Ruschhaupt, S. Pohlmann, A. Varzi, S. Passerini, *Batteries & Supercaps* **2020**, *3*, 698–707.
- 509 [58] D. Weingarth, A. Foelske-Schmitz, R. Kötz, *Journal of Power Sources* **2013**, *225*, 84–88.
- 510 [59] N. Handa, T. Sugimoto, M. Yamagata, M. Kikuta, M. Kono, M. Ishikawa, *Journal of Power Sources*
511 **2008**, *185*, 1585–1588.

- 512 [60] M. P. S. Mousavi, B. E. Wilson, S. Kashfolgheta, E. L. Anderson, S. He, P. Bühlmann, A. Stein,
513 *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* **2016**, *8*, 3396–3406.
- 514 [61] A. M., A. Paul, *ACS Omega* **2017**, *2*, 8039–8050.
- 515 [62] O. Chernysh, V. Khomenko, I. Makyeyeva, V. Barsukov, *Materials Today: Proceedings* **2019**, *6*, 42–
516 47.
- 517 [63] N. Susarla, S. Ahmed, D. W. Dees, *Journal of Power Sources* **2018**, *378*, 660–670.
- 518 [64] D. L. Wood, J. D. Quass, J. Li, S. Ahmed, D. Ventola, C. Daniel, *Drying Technology* **2018**, *36*, 234–
519 244.
- 520 [65] S. Menne, T. Vogl, A. Balducci, *Chemical Communications* **2015**, *51*, 3656–3659.
- 521 [66] H. Matsumoto, H. Sakaebe, K. Tatsumi, M. Kikuta, E. Ishiko, M. Kono, *Journal of Power Sources*
522 **2006**, *160*, 1308–1313.
- 523 [67] D. T. Rogstad, M.-A. Einarsrud, A. M. Svensson, *Journal of The Electrochemical Society* **2021**, *168*,
524 110506.
- 525 [68] A. P. Lewandowski, A. F. Hollenkamp, S. W. Donne, A. S. Best, *Journal of Power Sources* **2010**,
526 *195*, 2029–2035.
- 527 [69] I. A. Shkrob, T. W. Marin, Y. Zhu, D. P. Abraham, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2014**, *118*,
528 19661–19671.
- 529 [70] Z. Song, X. Wang, H. Wu, W. Feng, J. Nie, H. Yu, X. Huang, M. Armand, H. Zhang, Z. Zhou,
530 *Journal of Power Sources Advances* **2022**, *14*, 100088.
- 531 [71] H.-B. Han, S.-S. Zhou, D.-J. Zhang, S.-W. Feng, L.-F. Li, K. Liu, W.-F. Feng, J. Nie, H. Li, X.-J.
532 Huang, M. Armand, Z.-B. Zhou, *Journal of Power Sources* **2011**, *196*, 3623–3632.
- 533 [72] H. Ji, X. Zhao, Z. Qiao, J. Jung, Y. Zhu, Y. Lu, L. L. Zhang, A. H. MacDonald, R. S. Ruoff, *Nature*
534 *Communications* **2014**, *5*, 3317.
- 535 [73] D. Weingarh, M. Zeiger, N. Jäckel, M. Aslan, G. Feng, V. Presser, *Advanced Energy Materials*

- 536 **2014**, *4*, 1400316.
- 537 [74] T. S. Mathis, N. Kurra, X. Wang, D. Pinto, P. Simon, Y. Gogotsi, *Advanced Energy Materials* **2019**,
538 *9*, 1902007.
- 539 [75] R. Borah, F. R. Hughson, J. Johnston, T. Nann, *Materials Today Advances* **2020**, *6*, 100046.
- 540 [76] <https://en.solvionic.com/products/1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium-bisfluorosulfonylimide-99.5>,
541 accessed on 22/12/2024.
- 542 [77] L. Köps, F. A. Kreth, D. Leistenschneider, K. Schutjajew, R. Gläßner, M. Oschatz, A. Balducci,
543 *Advanced Energy Materials* **2023**, *13*, 2203821.
- 544 [78] E. Cho, J. Mun, O. B. Chae, O. M. Kwon, H.-T. Kim, J. H. Ryu, Y. G. Kim, S. M. Oh,
545 *Electrochemistry Communications* **2012**, *22*, 1–3.
- 546 [79] C. Li, S. Zeng, P. Wang, Z. Li, L. Yang, D. Zhao, J. Wang, H. Liu, S. Li, *Transactions of Nonferrous*
547 *Metals Society of China* **2021**, *31*, 1439–1451.
- 548 [80] E. Pameté, L. Köps, F. A. Kreth, S. Pohlmann, A. Varzi, T. Brousse, A. Balducci, V. Presser,
549 *Advanced Energy Materials* **2023**, *13*, 2301008.
- 550 [81] H. Lu, S. Zeng, D. Zhao, J. Wang, Y. Quan, F. Xu, F. Li, S. Li, *RSC Advances* **2021**, *11*, 26102–
551 26109.
- 552 [82] I. A. Shkrob, K. Z. Pupek, D. P. Abraham, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2016**, *120*, 18435–
553 18444.
- 554 [83] A. Leonard, B. Planden, K. Lukow, D. Morrey, *Journal of Energy Storage* **2023**, *72*, 108422.
- 555 [84] J. Cannarella, C. B. Arnold, *Journal of Power Sources* **2014**, *245*, 745–751.
- 556 [85] D. Cericola, R. Kötz, A. Wokaun, *Journal of Power Sources* **2011**, *196*, 3114–3118.
- 557 [86] L. Zhang, L. Chai, L. Zhang, M. Shen, X. Zhang, V. S. Battaglia, T. Stephenson, H. Zheng,
558 *Electrochimica Acta* **2014**, *127*, 39–44.
- 559

TOC

Ionogel-based electrodes, fabricated using an ionic liquid (EMIFSI) via a sustainable slurry casting method, eliminating costly filling steps while enabling high-performance EDLCs. These devices demonstrate 30+ Wh/kg energy density, superior rate capability and high-temperature operation up to 180°C, outperforming conventional EDLCs. A step forward for next-gen energy storage.